

A NUMERICAL STUDY TO INVESTIGATE THE EFFECT OF APPLICATION OF A POLYUREA LAYER ON ENERGY ABSORPTION OF SANDWICH SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Energy absorption in a sandwich panel is the most important parameter in a blast or impact scenario. The present work investigates the effect that an elastomeric material layer of polyurea can have on this parameter. As a starting point in the present work a steel beam has been studied under pulse loading. Alterations to the frequencies of the beam when a layer of polyurea is attached are studied using a linear perturbation method. Specific kinetic and strain energy variations for the steel beam with and without polyurea have been compared when subjected to a blast load using dynamic explicit finite element analysis. Subsequently, a shock load is applied on a sandwich panel with glass fibre reinforced plastic (GFRP) faces and balsa wood core and its polyurea strengthened counterpart. Material and geometric nonlinearities are allowed and damage to the core is modelled using an anisotropic plasticity damage model along with a quadratic shear failure criterion suitable for balsa wood failure modelling. Comparison of specific kinetic and strain energies shows the effect a layer of polyurea can have on blast energy absorption of a sandwich system along with the limitations of its utilisation. The study shows the improvement in shear failure prevention of the core as a result of use of a layer of polyurea and a reduction in the level of kinetic and strain energies in the core.

Keywords: Sandwich panel, polyurea, energy absorption, anisotropic, frequency analysis

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been an ever-increasing interest in the offshore, defence and marine industries to further increase the application of composite materials in primary structural applications due to the significant advantages they offer over traditional metals by the virtue of their high specific strength and stiffness, buoyancy, resistance to harsh marine environments, non-magnetism and unique stealth characteristics. One of the efficient ways of using fibre reinforced composites is by utilising them as skins of sandwich panels. The skins are responsible for flexural resistance and strength and thus carry in-plane tensile and compressive loads. The core in a sandwich panel is responsible for shear resistance and is usually made of a light material with high shear strength such as a type of PVC foam or balsa wood. As far as static loads are concerned an increase in core thickness increases the moment capacity substantially though not much the weight. Figure 1 shows the schematic of a sandwich panel.

Figure 1: Schematic of a sandwich panel

When static loads are involved the level of stresses in the structure determines the acceptable or unacceptable design given the applied loads. In contradistinction, energy absorption capability of a structure is the most important parameter in evaluation of its blast resistance. As such, a suitable blast resistant design must take into account this parameter. In the past few years some research has been conducted on the use of elastomeric materials in conjunction with conventional designs to improve blast and impact resistance of sandwich structures and some promising results are obtained [1-5].

While static elastic and plastic properties of polyurea (PU) have been known to researchers for a long time it was not until recently that visco-elastic and visco-plastic behaviour of PU was properly characterized [1]. Shim and Mohr [1] conducted experiments using modified split Hopkinson pressure bars (SHPB) at low, intermediate and high strain rates. Using experimental data numerical finite element (FE) models can be set up and run and the results obtained can be correlated with test.

In a recent study Tekalur *et al* [2] conducted experiments on rectangular plates of plain-woven and layered composites, simply supported along two edges and free along the other two subjected to controlled blast in a shock tube. They drew two important conclusions based on their measurements done using a high-speed camera during the dynamic bending in the blast scenario: (1) the addition of a polyurea layer on the impacted face considerably increases the blast resistance, (2) sandwich materials prepared by stacking the polyurea between two composite skins had the best blast resistance compared to the layered and the composite plates.

Other researchers have reported enhancement in blast resistance of sandwich plates when PU is used [3-5]. Bahei-El-Din and Dvorak [3; 4] studied the effect of design modifications using PU on dynamic response of sandwich plates to impulse pressure loads. Their work demonstrated the role of interlayers in enhancing structural performance of sandwich plates under blast loads. Compared to conventional sandwich plate designs, the benefits gained from the modification were itemized as follows:

- (a) Energy absorption is increased due to protection of the foam core, and this reduces the kinetic energy imparted to the sandwich plate parts by 25–50%.
- (b) Compression in the crushable core is reduced by more than 50%.
- (c) Opening displacement at debonded facesheet/core interfaces is reduced by a factor

of five.

(d) Plate deflection is reduced by 15%.

(e) Curvature of the inner facesheet at the supports is substantially lowered, and this helps in reducing potential failure.

Given the novelty of the proposal of using PU in conjunction with composites the studies conducted in the literature are not numerous but the results are consistent and in good agreement with the conclusions drawn in the present work. The present study deals with energy absorption in a sandwich structure in a blast scenario with and without a layer of polyurea. A preliminary study on a one way steel member (a steel beam) with and without polyurea attached along with some test runs on sandwich panels provides guideline on how to best use polyurea. Polyurea has the best performance when used as an adjacent layer to the sandwich core which works in compression under blast load (Figure 2). Figure 3 shows the relative advantage that application of a polyurea layer can offer in protecting the core and reducing the maximum central deflection of the panel. Here the total thickness of the panel is preserved ($t_{c1}=t_{c2}+t_{PU}$) and the trade-off in weight favours the application of the PU layer. Alternative set-ups such as using polyurea under the tension skin or above the compression skin do not contribute to energy absorption of the panel, reducing the central deflection or the protection of the core and are deemed irrelevant.

Figure 2: (a) A sandwich panel with unprotected core, (b) the panel protected by a layer of polyurea (both along with geometric parameters)

Figure 2: Cont'd

Figure 3(a): the pattern of damage in the core of a sandwich panel with unprotected core
 (Total panel thickness=thickness of skins ($2t_s$) + thickness of core (t_{c1}))
 (Blue elements represent failed ones)

Figure 3(b): the pattern of damage in the core of a polyurea protected sandwich panel
 with polyurea attached to the compression skin from inside
 (Total thickness=thickness of skins ($2t_s$) + thickness of core (t_{c2}) + thickness of PU layer (t_{PU}))
 (Blue elements represent failed ones)

2. Numerical study of PU-enhanced steel and sandwich beams

As a point of departure a simply supported steel beam has been considered. This preliminary example is assumed to provide some insight into the behaviour of a more sophisticated structure with similar characteristics. The steel beam has been investigated numerically with and without a layer of PU attached to it on the face subjected to impulsive or dynamic blast loading (Figure 4). FE models have been set up and analysed using the explicit formulation in ABAQUS 6.8. Mesh density in such problems is dictated by the finer of the two mesh systems: one giving accurate results

for a spatially similar static load (in this case a uniformly distributed load (UDL)) and one accurately capturing the frequencies with high amplitude in the Fourier transform of the load. In this case the static considerations prevail.

Figure 4: (a) steel beam subjected to blast on the top, (b) PU-enhanced steel beam subjected to blast on the top (geometric properties provided)

This study is followed by a study of a similar case on a sandwich panel. Material properties of steel and PU as well as sandwich GFRP skins and balsa wood are provided in table 1.

Property Material	Density	Young's modulus	Shear modulus	Poisson's ratio	Yielding Stress	σ_{ture_y}	ϵ_y	σ_{ture_2}	ϵ_{st}
Steel	8.06e-6	195		0.3	0.25	0.2503	0.0013	0.254	0.014
Polyurea	1.02e-6	0.12		0.44	0.0045	0.0047	0.0375		
GRP	2.1e-6	E_{11} : 17	G_{13} : 2.9	γ_{13} : 0.24					
		E_{22} : 15	G_{32} : 3.2	γ_{21} : 0.05					
		E_{33} : 7.5	G_{21} : 3.2	γ_{23} : 0.05	Plasticity				
Balsa wood	5.2E-8	E_{11} : 0.12	G_{12} : 0.02	γ_{12} : 0.2	α_{12} :0	α_{44} :109.7	α_{11} :80.6	τ_c =0.02	
		E_{22} : 0.12	G_{23} : 0.157	γ_{23} : 0.02	α_{23} :0	α_{55} : 6.2	α_{22} :80.6	τ_1 :0.0127	ϵ_{p1} :0
		E_{33} : 3.9	G_{31} : 0.157	γ_{31} : 0.2	α_{31} :0	α_{66} : 6.2	α_{33} : 2	τ_2 :0.0137	ϵ_{p1} :0.1

Table 1: Material elastic and plastic properties

This study indicates that there is virtually no advantage in using PU in conjunction with steel in the configuration discussed. This is obvious from the comparison of the curves of kinetic (KE) and strain (SE) energies for the two models for a range of loading from impulsive to dynamic and response types including elastic and plastic deformations (Figure 5). The comparisons of maximum stress/strain and central deflection for different case have similar implications.

Figure 5(a): Compariosn of kinetic energies for the two models
(Pulse loading is in the dynamic range and the structure remains elastic)

Figure 5(b): Compariosn of strain energies for the two models
(Pulse loading is in the dynamic range and the structure remains elastic)

Figure 5 is concerned with dynamic loading when the structure experiences elastic and reversible deformations. When pulse loading is in the impulsive range and when

deformations include both elasticity and plasticity similar results are obtained. A possible reason for the lack of contribution of PU to the protection of steel beam is the huge difference in the elastic moduli of the two materials. Elastic modulus of steel is 4 orders of magnitude higher than that of PU, as table 1 suggests, which means by the time PU has experienced large deformations and has undergone some plasticity in a blast scenario the attached steel part has not yet been stressed. This result is important as elastic modulus of GRP is similarly 3 orders of magnitude higher than PU. This means the application of a layer of PU on the top of the sandwich panel similar to the case of the steel beam would have no benefit. In fact, as mentioned before, this is confirmed by authors in a preliminary study.

On the other hand all moduli (in-plane and through thickness) of balsa wood are close to that of PU which means it may be beneficial to use PU in a core adjacent set-up similar to that shown in Figure 2. Figure 6 shows the two sandwich panel configurations with all geometric parameters included and Figure 7 shows a comparison of kinetic and strain energies of the two models when subjected to a blast load due to a high explosive (e.g. TNT) detonation. It must, however, be noted that unlike previous cases adopted for the preliminary study the thickness of the balsa core is preserved.

Figure 6: (a) a sandwich panel with balsa core and GFRP skins, (b) a sandwich panel with balsa core, GFRP skins and a layer of PU under the compression skin

While strain energy (SE) is a reliable parameter for comparing the benefits of the new set-up compared to the conventional one, the validity of kinetic energy (KE) as a reliable parameter is subject to absence of rigid body modes (zero frequency modes). The sandwich beam (one-way panel) under consideration is simply supported and is thus free from rigid body modes. This means both parameters are reliable. These parameters are plotted for different cases.

(a)

- Figure 7:** (a) Comparison of kinetic energies when no core damage is observed
(b) Comparison of strain energies when no core damage is observed
(c) Comparison of kinetic energies when some core damage is observed
(d) Comparison of strain energies when some core damage is observed

(b)

(c)

Figure 7: Cont'd

(d)

Figure 7: Cont'd

3. Concluding remarks

The present work deals with application of a polyurea (PU) layer under the skin of a sandwich panel and the benefits this set-up offers in a blast loading scenario. Table 2 summarizes the results obtained from this study. An initial study on a steel beam enhanced with a layer of PU on the side facing the blast shows the lack of any benefit offered by PU to the blast resistance of the structure. Following a preliminary study on sandwich panels it was settled that the best way PU can be used to improve blast resistant capacity is to be used under the compression GFRP skin of the panel. Two cases have been studied here viz. when there is no damage to the core and when there is damage to the core. When there is no damage to the core the stress and energy levels are lower with PU compared to unenhanced sandwich panel. This in itself defers any damage to the core. When there is some damage to the core the damage is more restricted when PU is used and better performance is achieved. These results are summarized in Table 2.

Structure type	Loading type	Response regime	Kinetic Energy (KE)	Strain Energy (SE)	Maximum Principal Stress	Maximum Logarithmic Strain
Simply Supported Steel Panel	Dynamic Loading	<i>Elastic</i>	Slightly Reduced	Slightly Reduced	Slightly Reduced	Reduced at the steel side, slightly increased at the polyurea side
		<i>Plastic</i>	Slightly Increased	Slightly Increased	No effects	No effects
	Impulsive Loading	<i>Elastic</i>	Reduced	Reduced	Reduced	Reduced at the steel side, slightly increased at the polyurea side
		<i>Plastic</i>	Slightly Increased	Slightly Increased	No effects	Reduced
						State Variable
Simply Supported sandwich Panel	Dynamic Loading	<i>Without core failure</i>	Reduced	Reduced	Reduced	Reduced in panel core (less elements at incipient failure point)
		<i>With core failure</i>	Reduced	Slightly reduced	Reduced	Reduced in panel core (less failed elements)

Table 2: Summary of the results

4. References

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